

Mesoporous indium tin oxide enhances the electroenzymatic performance and stability of [FeFe]-hydrogenase during hydrogen production

Sophie Webb,^{[a][b]} Astrit Veliju,^[c] Plinio Maroni,^[a] Ulf-Peter Apfel,^{[d][e]} Thomas Happe,^[c] Ross D. Milton^{[a][b]*}

[a] S. Webb, P. Maroni and R. D. Milton
Department of Inorganic and Analytical Chemistry
University of Geneva
Faculty of Sciences, Quai Ernest-Ansermet 30, 1211 Geneva 4, Switzerland
E-mail: ross.milton@unige.ch

[b] S. Webb and Prof R. D. Milton
National Centre of Competence in Research (NCCR) Catalysis
University of Geneva
Switzerland

[c] A. Veliju and T. Happe
Faculty of Biology and Biotechnology
Photobiotechnology
Ruhr University Bochum
Germany

[d] U. Apfel
Inorganic Chemistry 1
Ruhr University Bochum
Germany

[e] U. Apfel
Department of Electrosynthesis
Fraunhofer UMSICHT
Oberhausen
Germany

Supporting information for this article is given via a link at the end of the document.

Abstract: The metalloenzyme [FeFe]-hydrogenase is of interest to future biotechnologies targeting the production of “green” hydrogen (H_2). We recently developed a simple two-step functionalized procedure to immobilize the [FeFe]-hydrogenase from *Clostridium pasteurianum* (“Cpl”) on mesoporous indium tin oxide (ITO) electrodes to achieve elevated H_2 production with high operational stability, with current densities of 8 mA cm^{-2} . Here, we use a combination of atomic force microscopy (AFM), scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and electrochemical quartz crystal microbalance (EQCM) to understand how mesoporous ITO stabilizes and activates Cpl for electroenzymatic H_2 production. Examination of the topography and morphology of the mesoporous ITO surface revealed a hierarchical morphology containing cavities and well-defined nanoparticle agglomerates. Any potential effect of mesoporosity was investigated by comparing the stability and electroenzymatic activity of Cpl on mesoporous ‘nanoITO’ and planar ITO, where we determined that Cpl adsorbs with greater stability (with respect to electroenzymatic activity over time) to nanoITO surfaces.

Introduction

Decarbonization of the energy sector is driving financial investment into “green” hydrogen (H_2), the majority of which is currently produced by water electrolysis.¹ Depending on the type of electrolyzer, high operational temperatures, caustic pH environments and precious metal catalysts may be required. Despite the attractiveness of H_2 production from renewable

electricity over fossil fuel-dependent “high emission” H_2 , such green H_2 currently accounts for only 0.1% of H_2 produced (2022).² The metalloenzyme [FeFe]-hydrogenase ([FeFe]-H₂ase) catalyzes H_2 evolution with a high turnover frequency (TOF) of up to $10,000 \text{ H}_2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, and operates under ambient conditions.³ [FeFe]-H₂ase contains a highly conserved active site called the ‘H-cluster’, which is comprised of a [2Fe] center coordinated to a [4Fe-4S] cluster via a cysteinyl thiolate residue.⁴ The distal [2Fe] center contains a vacant coordination site for proton (H^+) or H_2 binding and the Fe centers are covalently linked together by a bridging aza-dithiolate ligand which serves as a H^+ -delivering pendant.

The utility of enzymes like [FeFe]-H₂ase can be realized electrochemically by immobilizing them on an electrode and applying an overpotential to drive electroenzymatic H_2 evolution. To ensure efficient operation, the enzyme should be stable for extended time periods on the electrode surface and be immobilized in an orientation that ensures a fast rate of interfacial/heterogeneous electron transfer (k_{ET}). Thus, the term “stability” includes (i) the adsorption process, (ii) enzymatic activity, and (iii) k_{ET} between the electrode surface and the enzyme. Some immobilization strategies for [FeFe]-H₂ases include covalent tethering,⁵ electrostatic binding,⁶ and entrapment within a polymer-based matrix on the electrode surface.^{7,8} In spite of efficient immobilization, planar electrodes limit the mass of immobilized enzyme and often lower performance of the enzyme due to steric hinderance, slow mass transport diffusion rates and possible perturbation of the native enzyme structure on the

Figure 1: Electroenzymatic activity of *Cpl* as a function (a) nanoITO concentration (% w/v) and (b) *Cpl* concentration. Hydrogen evolution (HER) current density (j_{max}) extracted at -0.8 V vs. SHE from cyclic voltammograms as a function of (a) the density of ITO nanoparticle suspension drop-cast on GC and (b) the concentration of *Cpl* drop-cast on nanoITO film (fixed at 20 % w/v). The inset of (a) reports a representative CV of a *Cpl*-nanoITO electrode prepared with 20 % w/v nanoITO and 53 μ M *Cpl*, and indicates the potential at which j_{max} was extracted on each CV (grey dashed line). A concentration dependent (black data points) and concentration independent (blue data points) regime of electrocatalytic activity can be identified in both graphs. All CVs were performed in 0.1 M MOPS buffer (stirred) at 22 °C and at a scan rate of 10 mV s⁻¹. Red asterisks indicate the concentration of nanoITO or *Cpl* which is fixed in the other graph. Each data point represents the minimum current density value extracted at -0.8 V vs. SHE on the third cyclic of each CV experiment.

electrode surface.⁹ The use of redox polymers is attractive since electron transfer from the electrode is effectively extended throughout a three-dimensional enzyme:polymer network, where a covalently tethered redox-active species facilitates electron transfer to/from the enzyme as well as self-exchange throughout the enzyme:polymer network (termed “mediated electron transfer”, MET).¹⁰ While the use of a redox polymer arguably adds another layer of complexity to electrode design, added benefits such as (i) auto-protection and (ii) fine tunability of electroenzymatic catalytic bias cannot be ignored.^{7,11} Herein, we focus on direct electron transfer (DET) where the enzyme engages in heterogeneous electron transfer with the electrode surface in the absence of an additional redox-active species.^{12,13}

To circumvent the issues associated with DET on planar electrodes, alternative materials such as nanotubes,^{14–16} fibers,¹⁷ felts,¹⁸ and dots are popular options to immobilize H₂ases.¹⁹ Mesoporous materials also contain architectures which improve enzyme wiring, where the immobilization of enzymes in pores 1 - 3 times their size display increased activity due to multiple enzyme-pore contact points, which increases k_{ET}.^{20,21} Spatial confinement of the enzyme also helps maintain its native confirmation and reduces the probability of denaturation, whilst larger pores allow for efficient mass transport within the meso-structure.¹²

Hierarchical mesoporous metal oxides such as TiO₂ and ITO (indium tin oxide) have been used in combination with [FeFe]-H₂ases to reach benchmark H₂ evolution current densities.^{23,24} We recently reported a simple two-step technique for the facile functionalization of carbon electrodes with a mesoporous ITO (“nanoITO”), onto which the [FeFe]-H₂ase from *Clostridium pasteurianum* (“*Cpl*”) was subsequently immobilized for direct electron transfer.²⁵ Cyclic voltammetry (CV) of the enzyme

electrode yielded high current densities of > 8 mA cm⁻² at -0.8 V vs. SHE (pH 7) for H₂ production, with ~ 92 % of the original current density maintained following 5 days of continuous potentiostatic operation.

Unexpectedly, we previously observed that the current density for H₂ production on nanoITO was >38 times greater in comparison to *Cpl* deposited on planar glassy carbon (GC) electrodes, which we hypothesized may be simply explained by an increase in electrode surface area (the electrochemically active surface area “ECSA”). Here, we report that this is not the case and that nanoconfinement of *Cpl* on the nanoITO electrode results in enhanced and prolonged electroenzymatic H₂ production in terms of both magnitude and stability.

Results and Discussion

NanoITO film loading and mesoporosity influences electroenzymatic performance of *Cpl* [FeFe]-hydrogenase

NanoITO enzyme electrodes were prepared by a simple two-step procedure: a suspension of ITO nanoparticles was drop-casted on a 3 mm GC electrode and annealed in an oven at 80 °C, after which a solution of *Cpl* was drop-cast on the ITO surface in an Ar-filled glovebox for 10 min prior to electrochemical evaluation (Supplementary Fig. 1). Importantly, no additional measures were taken to ensure the immobilization of *Cpl* on the nanoITO surface. As per our previous report, the nanoITO surface was initially prepared with a 20 % w/v suspension of ITO nanoparticles, which formed an optically homogenous film with a thickness of 10.5 μ m.²⁵

Figure 2: Electrochemical surface area (ECSA) of the nanoITO film (black points) and film thickness (blue points), plotted as a function of ITO nanoparticle (nanoITO) loading. The ECSA technique was used to calculate the nanoITO film capacitance, in $F\text{ cm}^{-2}$, by CV under diffusion control in 0.1 M KCl at 22 °C. The ratio between the surface capacitance of the nanoITO film and a planar ITO surface, at identical ITO compositions (In:Sn 9:1) and known surface area (0.78 cm^2) yields the nanoITO film electroactive surface area in cm^2 (left-side y-axis, black data points). NanoITO film thickness, extracted from optical microscopy images, is plotted a function of nanoITO film % w/v (right-side y-axis, blue data points). ECSA is reported as a mean \pm SD, while film thickness is extracted an optical microscope image at each nanoITO % w/v, as shown in Supplementary Fig. 3.2.

To investigate the relationship between ITO film thickness, electrode meso-structure, and enzyme electrode performance, different quantities of nanoparticles (achieved by altering the density of the ITO suspensions between 1 – 30 % w/v) were used to prepared enzyme electrodes with a fixed concentration of *Cpl* (Fig. 1a). The enzyme electrode performance was assessed electrochemically via CV by extracting a maximum current density value (j_{max}) at -0.8 V vs. SHE (Fig. 1a inset) at a *Cpl* concentration of $53\text{ }\mu\text{M}$ and reporting this as a function of nanoITO % w/v. Similarly, to assess the effect of *Cpl* concentration on electroenzymatic performance, a titration was performed between 0.8 - $53\text{ }\mu\text{M}$ *Cpl* at a fixed ITO nanoparticle concentration of 20 % w/v (Fig. 1b). At lower concentrations of ITO and *Cpl*, the current density increases linearly (Fig. 1, black data), followed by a plateau region (Fig. 1, blue data) where the maximum current density (j_{max}) remains relatively constant, despite increasing concentrations of ITO and *Cpl*. We hypothesize that, at a lower loading of ITO, j_{max} is limited by the mass of adsorbed *Cpl* since the ITO surface area is not large enough to immobilize all the applied enzyme. After the inflection points of (i) 10 % w/v nanoITO (using $53\text{ }\mu\text{M}$ *Cpl*, Fig. 1a) and (ii) 17.5 μM *Cpl* (using 20 % w/v nanoITO, Fig. 1b), j_{max} becomes constant. We set an upper limit of 20 % w/v ITO nanoparticles for the optimization of *Cpl*, since the ITO nanoparticle film becomes optically heterogeneous beyond this loading (Supplementary Fig. 3.1). The total electrochemical surface area (calculated by comparing the capacitance of nanoITO (Supplementary Fig. 4.1) and planar ITO films (Supplementary Fig. 4.2) at higher ITO loadings may not be

accessible to the enzyme due to the morphology, or at higher loadings of ITO nanoparticles the enzyme cannot fully penetrate the layer as the film is too thick (the 30 % w/v ITO layer has a film thickness of $28.2\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ (Supplementary Fig. 3.2)). The presence of the plateau regions in Fig. 1 could also indicate a mass transport limitation in thicker ITO films, due to impeded H^+/H_2 ingress and egress. During continuous H_2 production at the enzyme electrode, it is also possible that a local pH gradient is formed within and at the interface of the ITO film.²⁶

To understand how the ITO architecture changes with film depth, the electrochemical surface area (ECSA) at each loading of ITO was compared to film thickness, as measured by optical microscopy (Fig. 2). The formation of a homogenous ITO film from 10 % w/v and above can be observed by eye (Supplementary Fig. 3.1) and by optical light microscopy (Supplementary Fig. 3.2). In Fig. 2, the ITO capacitance scales with film thickness, indicating that the internal structure (meso-porosity) of the film does not vary significantly with increasing film thickness. A similar trend of film thickness vs. nanoITO % w/v has been previously reported.²⁷ The non-linear increase in ECSA and film thickness at 30 % w/v ITO loading could indicate increased flocculation of ITO nanoparticles in higher density ITO suspensions (each ITO suspension sample was pipetted at a fixed depth near the bottom of the tube). AFM was used to analyze the topography of a 1, 10, and 30 % w/v ITO film over an area of $25\text{ }\mu\text{m}^2$ (Fig. 3). The similarity in the height profile and roughness factor (R_{ms}) of each ITO film indicates that the topography is independent of the loading of ITO nanoparticles. Spherical ITO agglomerates between 60 – 80 nm are composed of smaller sub-structures below 80 nm. These agglomerates may contain pore sizes favorable for *Cpl* immobilization. The porosity of a 30 % w/v nanoITO film was also evaluated by cross-sectional scanning electron microscopy (SEM), which was found to be heterogeneous (Fig. 4a and b), with pores varying from 15-20 μm . Under greater magnification (Fig. 4c), well-defined ITO nanoparticle agglomerates ranging from 500 nm – 1 μm are observed, consistent with the structures observed by AFM in Fig. 3. Smaller pores of less than 5 μm in diameter are present in the cross-section of this sample. Introducing a distribution of nanopores, micropores and mesopores with a porous electrode allows concurrent efficient mass transport, enzyme immobilization and incorporation of advantageous edge and curvature effects which may enhance enzymatic performance.²⁰ Smaller pores present between the ITO agglomerates may stabilize *Cpl*, whilst larger cracks and cavities could permit efficient mass transport through ITO film.²² Representative images of the full nanoITO cross-section are shown in Supplementary Fig. 3.3.

[FeFe]- H_2 ase is sensitive to deactivation by molecular oxygen (O_2). Previously, we employed this as a control measure to verify that the observed electroenzymatic currents for H_2 production were indeed due to [FeFe]- H_2 ase and not the underlying ITO nanoparticle surface.²⁵ However, we could not exclude that the H_2 formed is not due to denatured *Cpl* which had lost its [2Fe] cofactor and whose subsequent adsorption to the ITO surface resulted in electrocatalytic (not electroenzymatic) H_2 formation. To address this question we employed apo-*Cpl*, which lacks the [2Fe]^{ADT} cofactor ($\text{Fe}_2[\mu\text{-}(\text{SCH}_2)_2\text{NH}](\text{CN})_2(\text{CO})_4^{2-}$ complex) and can be artificially reconstituted.²⁸ NanoITO electrodes were

Figure 3: Atomic force microscope (AFM) images of 1, 10 and 30 % w/v nanoITO surfaces (5 μm x 5 μm), measured in constant amplitude modulation mode. A corresponding z-axis height profile (nm) of each AFM image (extracted at $y = 2.5 \mu\text{m}$, as indicated by the black dashed arrow), and surface roughness factor (R_{ms}) is extracted and reported below each image as a mean \pm SD.

prepared with either apo-*Cpl* or synthetic $[\text{2Fe}]^{\text{ADT}}$ cofactor, and subsequently treated with the missing counterpart (i.e., $[\text{2Fe}]^{\text{ADT}}$ cofactor or apo-*Cpl*). As shown in Fig. 5, the presence of either the synthetic $[\text{2Fe}]^{\text{ADT}}$ cofactor or the apo-*Cpl* enzyme alone did not yield a significant electrocatalytic current for H_2 formation. The subsequent addition of either missing component to yield in vitro-reconstituted *Cpl* resulted in a clear electroenzymatic current for H_2 formation. We conclude that electrocatalytic H_2 production on *Cpl*:nanoITO enzyme electrodes is therefore strictly electroenzymatic in nature, and not due to partially (or completely) denatured *Cpl* or free $[\text{2Fe}]^{\text{ADT}}$ cofactor.

High activity of $[\text{FeFe}]$ -hydrogenase *Cpl* prevents electroreduction of nanoITO

ITO is already in an oxidized form (In_2O_3 , SnO_2) and therefore more stable within the anodic, than cathodic potential window. The onset potential for electrochemical ITO reduction shifts more positively with decreasing pH and is also dependent on the electrochemical buffer species.²⁹ Irreversible reduction is observed alongside an electrochromic effect and loss of conductivity, as indium and tin oxides in the film are reduced to form metallic particles, and often accompanied by the H_2 evolution reaction (HER).²⁹ We therefore investigated whether ITO reduction occurs within the operational potentials of the *Cpl* bioelectrode and evaluated the possible implications for applications of this bioelectrode. A relatively strongly reductive potential of -1.1 V (vs. SHE) was applied for 120 s and CV was subsequently performed to characterize the resulting nanoITO surface. When *Cpl* is not adsorbed to the nanoITO electrode surface, increased capacitance is observed in addition to a new, non-enzymatic, reductive current from -0.6 to -0.8 V (Fig. 6a, red line). A broad oxidative peak was observed from -0.6 to -0.2 V , which we attribute to the oxidation of reduced In and Sn oxides or metallic In^0 and Sn^0 on the surface. CV was also utilized directly to induce ITO reduction (Supplementary Fig. 5.1), where the sequential reductive and oxidative processes can be more clearly

identified.³⁰ Upon significant H_2 evolution, the mechanical integrity of ITO is also weakened and may promote film disintegration,³¹ as observed in Supplementary Fig. 5.1 when the current magnitude decreases upon continuous potential cycling. The electrochromic effect during reduction is also observed as the film color transitions from a blue/green to dark grey (Fig. 6a) as metallic regions of In and Sn accumulate on the surface. A very similar response is observed when *Cpl* is replaced with catalytically inactive bovine serum albumin (BSA) protein (Fig. 6a, yellow). Interestingly, reductive treatment of the ITO electrode in the presence of *Cpl* does not result in this behaviour. Instead, a typical voltammogram for electroenzymatic H_2 production is observed (Fig. 6a, blue). We hypothesize that the high electroenzymatic activity (and intrinsic TOF) of *Cpl* effectively results in electrons produced at the electrode surface (when E_{applied} is sufficient) being directed towards *Cpl* for electroenzymatic H_2 production prior to ITO reduction, thereby preventing the reduction currents observed in its absence. This implies that caution should be exercised when utilizing less-active enzymes within the cathodic window as this may lead to accelerated ITO reduction.

HER at electrochemically reduced ITO is also a universal occurrence when exceeding the potential limit stability of an aqueous solvent.³² We employed rotating ring disk electrochemistry (RRDE) to verify if the large reductive current density observed in Fig. 6a could indeed be attributed to HER at the ITO surface following electrochemical reduction, with a Pt ring electrode serving as a H_2 collector.^{8,33,34} As the ITO film is relatively thick, we expected that a perturbed laminar flow could decrease the collection efficiency (CE) of H_2 at the Pt ring. To validate this hypothesis, *Cpl* was first immobilized on ITO to determine an 'effective' maximum empirical CE for H_2 detection based on previous evidence that H^+ reduction *via Cpl* on ITO occurs with 100% Faradic efficiency under these conditions (verified by gas chromatography).²⁵ The GC disk electrode was functionalized with nanoITO in the absence and presence of

Figure 4: Scanning electron microscope (SEM) images of a 30 % w/v nanoITO cross section, recorded at an electron acceleration voltage of 10 keV and at magnifications of (a) x 500 (b) x 1,500 and (c) x 3,700 at an acceleration voltage of 10 keV and a working distance of 9.5 mm.

additional *Cpl* and the surrounding Pt ring was poised at a potential of 0 V vs. SHE to quantitatively re-oxidize the electroenzymatically produced H_2 (Fig. 6b). The collection efficiency at -0.8 V was found to be 9.6 %, lower than theoretical CE of 24.9 % for this electrode.⁸ At this fixed ITO film height, we therefore take 9.6 % as an effective maximum collection efficiency.

When the Pt ring was poised at 0 V vs. SHE, in the absence of *Cpl*, Supplementary Fig. 5.2a shows little to no H_2 is detected on the ring before the application of a strongly reducing potential to the nanoITO film. After applying a potential of -1.1 V vs. SHE, the ITO film is reduced and the current detected on the ring increases to $0.75 \mu A$ (Supplementary Fig. 5.2b), indicating that some H_2 is produced in the electrochemical cell during the application of this low potential; this is expected as the experiment is at the limit of the solvent window. CV of this reduced ITO electrode confirms that H_2 is indeed produced between -0.6 to -0.8 V vs. SHE in the absence of *Cpl*, although (i) the H_2 CE is 0.9 % (Supplementary Fig. 5.2b) (approximately 10x lower than the CE for *Cpl* electrodes), and (ii) a much larger overpotential for significant H_2

production is required in the absence of *Cpl* (Fig. 6b). Thus, H_2 production is a minor reaction on ITO in the absence of a bioelectrocatalyst such as *Cpl* (under these conditions), and the remaining Faradaic processes are likely related to ITO reduction or conversion at the electrode surface (or perhaps a reaction with the MOPS buffer, which is not detected on the Pt ring electrode).

Mesoporous ITO morphology enhances the electrochemical performance and stability of [FeFe]-hydrogenase *Cpl*

We previously observed that *Cpl* remains electrocatalytically active for extended periods on the nanoITO surface.²⁵ To determine whether this is due to the mesoporous structure of nanoITO, the real-time adsorption, stability, and electrochemical activity of *Cpl* was evaluated on a mesoporous and planar ITO electrode surface using EQCM. *Note: We are practically limited to a significantly smaller ITO nanoparticle film when using EQCM as compared to those prepared on 3 mm GC electrodes. A thicker ITO film cannot be used due to increased dissipation and overdamping of the system, which leads to loss of the crystal resonance frequency.*

The bare planar and nanoITO surfaces both behave as a ridged film, displaying little-to-no difference between harmonic overtone frequencies (Supplementary Fig. 6.1). It is therefore assumed when *Cpl* is adsorbed on both ITO surfaces it is fully coupled to oscillation of the quartz microbalance crystal and the Sauerbrey equation can be applied to estimate the mass of *Cpl* adsorbing to the ITO surface in real time, under conditions of laminar flow. The electrochemical activity of *Cpl* was monitored simultaneously under a constant applied potential of -424 mV vs. SHE (i.e., applied overpotential (η) of -10 mV ($E_{2H^+/H_2}^0 = -414$ mV vs. SHE at pH 7). Additional data suggests that there was little effect of varying applied potential on the electrochemical stability (Supplementary Fig. 6.2) and adsorbed mass (Supplementary Fig. 6.3) of immobilized *Cpl*.

The difference in adsorption behaviour of *Cpl* on planar and mesoporous ITO (with the same chemical composition of 9:1 In:Sn) is shown in Fig. 7a and Fig. 7b. The *Cpl* adsorption profile is similar in both cases: adsorption begins quickly and then reaches a plateau, indicating that adsorption of *Cpl* is complete. While the capacitance (reflecting the ECSA) of the mesoporous

Figure 5: Artificial maturation of apo-*Cpl* with $[2Fe]^{ADT}$ cofactor on the nanoITO surface to yield the active holo-*Cpl* enzyme achieved through (a) immobilization of apo-*Cpl* first (black dashed line), and $[2Fe]^{ADT}$ cofactor second (black solid line), and (b) immobilization of $[2Fe]^{ADT}$ cofactor first (blue dashed line), and apo-*Cpl* second (blue solid line). CVs were performed in 0.1 M MOPS buffer (stirred) at 22 °C and at a scan rate of 10 mV s^{-1} and the third cycle of each CV experiment is shown.

Figure 5: NanoITO electroreduction characterized by cyclic voltammetry (a) performed on a 3 mm GC|nanoITO electrode before (black dashed line) and after (pink solid line) reductive treatment (-1.1 V vs. SHE, 120 s). The reductive procedure was applied to nanoITO bioelectrodes fabricated with the electro-inactive BSA protein (yellow solid line) or Cpl, which was able to prevent electroreduction of the nanoITO film (blue solid line). Inset pictures demonstrate the electrochromic effect which is observed following reductive treatment of nanoITO surface in the absence of Cpl. (b) RRDE of a GC|nanoITO-Cpl disk (blue solid line) and Pt ring (black solid line) electrode during electroenzymatic H_2 production at a rotation rate (ω) of 2000 rpm, displaying a maximum collection efficiency of 9.6 % at -0.8 V vs. SHE. CVs were performed in 0.1 M MOPS buffer at 22 °C and at a scan rate of 10 mV s $^{-1}$. The third cycle of each CV experiment is shown.

ITO surface was 2.5x larger than that of the planar ITO surface (Supplementary Fig. 6.4), only 1.5x more Cpl could be immobilized. Thus, we conclude that a portion of the nanoITO film contains morphologies unavailable for Cpl immobilization, perhaps with pores smaller in size than that of the enzyme (Fig. 3).

The efficient electroenzymatic performance of Cpl on mesoporous ITO can be discerned by comparing the maximum current magnitude (i_{max}) during electroenzymatic H^+ reduction to that of Cpl immobilized on planar ITO, after normalizing for the adsorbed Cpl mass (Fig. 7a and Fig. 7b). Under a mild η of -10 mV ($E^0_{2H^+/H_2} = -414$ mV vs. SHE at pH 7), the electrochemical activity of Cpl on mesoporous ITO was observed to be 2.9x greater than planar ITO. Further, the effective TOFs for Cpl immobilized on planar and mesoporous ITO were calculated to be 14 s $^{-1}$ and 41 s $^{-1}$, respectively (Table S6.5), reflecting that Cpl is 2.9x more electroactive for H^+ reduction on nanoITO than planar ITO. The isoelectric point of ITO is approximately pH 6, and therefore negatively charged when the Cpl solution is drop-cast (150 mM NaCl, 100 mM Tris, pH 8).³⁵ Furthermore, Cpl harbors a region of positively charged residues around the surface-exposed and site-differentiated [4Fe-4S] cluster, enabling ferredoxin docking *in vivo*.³⁶ We suggest the electrostatic interaction between ITO and this positive surface region of Cpl controls the adsorption of the enzyme into an electroactive configuration, which is independent of the ITO surface morphology. This hypothesis is supported as the catalytic current magnitude increases on both ITO morphologies in parallel with the mass of immobilized Cpl, until i_{max} is reached (Fig. 7a and Fig. 7b). However, with CV the electrocatalytic current observed below ~ -0.4 V vs. SHE (for electroenzymatic H_2 production) increases linearly with the applied potential over a relatively large potential window of approximately 400 mV; unexpectedly, a mass transport limitation-induced plateau is not readily observed (inset, Fig. 1a). This observation is consistent with the model proposed earlier by Christophe Léger and co-workers, whereby the adsorption of

enzymes on electrode surfaces can result in a dispersion of enzyme orientations, and thus, a dispersion of interfacial k_{ET} .³⁷ More recently, Davis and co-workers observed that the presence of a His-tag on [NiFe]-hydrogenases results in uniform adsorption of the enzyme on ITO surfaces;³⁸ a feat not offered by the Strep-tagged Cpl used in our work. Thus, we hypothesize that mesoporous ITO electrodes, in contrast to planar ITO electrodes, provide an abundance of electrostatically favorable surfaces for the adsorption of Cpl in many different orientations that result in enzymatic electrocatalysis with heterogeneous interfacial k_{ET} . The stability of Cpl on planar and mesoporous ITO was also assessed by continuously flowing 0.1 M MOPS buffer through the EQCM cell after Cpl immobilization was complete and observing any changes in mass or current over a period of 2 h 45 min (10,000 s). The stability data contains artifacts due to unavoidable H_2 bubble formation (Fig. 7a, grey dashed line) and temperature fluctuations (Fig. 7b, black dotted data), however we can say with high confidence that the adsorbed mass of Cpl does not change substantially on either surface during the experiment (i.e., Cpl adsorption is relatively stable, Fig. 6a). This is in agreement with literature which reports the strong electrostatic interaction between ITO surfaces and proteins.^{38–40} After normalizing the current trace on both surfaces, the electrochemical data can be more accurately compared (Fig. 7c). On planar ITO, i_{max} is reached after 17 min compared to nanoITO, which takes 63 min. This difference can be rationalized by comparing the initial adsorption kinetics of Cpl on ITO, which was similar on planar and mesoporous ITO (Supplementary Fig. 6.6). We suggest the adsorption regime on mesoporous ITO is simply longer because the total quantity of Cpl immobilized is larger.

We compared the electroenzymatic stability of Cpl over 2 hr 45 min (10,000 s) between nanoITO and planar ITO. The electrochemical stability of Cpl (i.e., current magnitude over time) following i_{max} is very clearly maintained on mesoporous ITO for the full 2 hr 45 min (10,000 s), whereas the i_{max} in planar ITO steadily decreases until reaching 40 % of the initial i_{max} value after

Figure 7: EQCM *Cpl* adsorption profiles and current response on planar ITO and mesoporous 'nanoITO' films at $E_{\text{applied}} = -424$ mV vs. SHE (-10 mV overpotential w.r.t. $E^{\circ}_{2\text{H}^+/\text{H}_2}$) on (a) planar ITO surface showing adsorbed *Cpl* mass (black solid line) and current (blue solid line) and (b) the nanoITO surface showing adsorbed *Cpl* mass (black solid line) and current (red solid line) and (c) and the normalized electrocatalytic current response of *Cpl* from (a) and (b) where $i_{\text{max}} = 1$ in both cases. *Cpl* adsorption was performed from a 5 ppm solution in 0.1 M MOPS buffer (pH 7) at 22 °C and at a flow rate of 1 mL/min.

2 hr 45 min (10,000 s) (Fig. 7c). We hypothesize that the mesoporous ITO film contains morphologies which may confine *Cpl*, as there has been evidence to suggest confining enzymes in pores 1-3 times their size can increase electrochemical and thermal stability.^{20,21} The surface morphology of ITO therefore seems to play a significant role in preserving the electrochemical activity of the enzyme over extended periods.²⁵

Conclusion

In conclusion, we propose that mesoporous ITO ('nanoITO') electrodes can stabilize the [FeFe]-hydrogenase (*Cpl*) for stable, improved electroenzymatic H_2 production over planar surfaces of similar chemistry. Using EQCM, we observed that the electrostatically driven adsorption of *Cpl* on planar and mesoporous ITO was independent of ITO surface morphology, and strong enough to prevent desorption of the enzyme over a period of 2 hr 45 min (10,000 s). Our key finding is that the morphology of mesoporous ITO results in *Cpl* being 2.9x more active for electrocatalytic H^+ reduction. We suggest the morphology of mesoporous ITO prevents enzyme denaturation by restricting enzyme movement and thus maintaining a native conformation. Mesoporous structures may also yield improved stability (in terms of adsorbed mass) due to the possibility of having multiple electrostatic interactions before the loss of enzyme into the bulk. Echoing this, SEM confirms that the ITO mesoporous structure is rough and inhomogeneous, containing large cavities between 15 – 20 μm , and on closer inspection formed well-defined nanoparticle agglomerates between 500 nm – 1 μm , with many interstitial cavities. We suggest that this hierarchical morphology may also enable efficient mass transport. In the absence of *Cpl*, the ITO film underwent critical and irreversible electrochemical reduction, where conductivity was lost, and film disintegration occurred. When utilizing enzymes with lower TOFs and/or applying potentials below -1.1 V, it is therefore important to consider that electrons may be diverted towards this undesirable side reaction. We expect that further elucidation of the interaction between *Cpl* and 'nanoITO' will provide additional information to aid in the application of the 'nanoITO' electrode with

other redox metalloenzymes such as formate dehydrogenase for carbon dioxide reduction, or nitrogenase for ammonia production.

Supporting Information

The authors have cited additional references within the Supporting Information.^[25]

Acknowledgements

We thank James Swartz for sharing *E. coli* BL21(DE3) ΔiscR and the plasmids for *Cpl* production. We thank all members of the Milton group, in particular, Olivier Vassalli, Daniel Ratcliff and Darren Martin. We thank Jérôme Bosset of the UNIGE Photonic Bioimaging Center for assistance with scanning electron microscopy.

Contributor Roles

All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript. The project was conceived by SW, PM and RM. SW and PM performed the experiments and initial data analysis. AV and UPA prepared the materials for the apo-*Cpl* experiments, and SW and AV performed the apo-*Cpl* electrochemical experiments and data analysis. UPA, TH and RM supervised and funded the work. SW prepared the initial draft of the manuscript; all authors contributed to the final version of the manuscript.

Funding Sources

This publication was created as part of the NCCR Catalysis (grant number 180544, to S.W. and R.D.M.), a National Centre of Competence in Research funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation. A.V., U-P.A. and T.H. acknowledge the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) under Germany's Excellence

Strategy – EXC 2033 – 390677874 – RESOLV. T. H. thanks the DFG (HA 2555/10-1) and the VolkswagenStiftung (Az 98621) for financial support. U-P.A. was supported by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, AP242/12-1).

Keywords: Direct electron transfer • [FeFe]-hydrogenase • Hydrogen • Indium tin oxide • Mesoporous

- [1] M. Nasser, T. F. Megahed, S. Ookawara, H. Hassan, *Environ Sci Pollut Res* **2022**, *29*, 86994–87018.
- [2] IEA (2023), *Global Hydrogen Review 2023*, IEA, Paris <https://www.iea.org/reports/global-hydrogen-review-2023>, Licence: CC BY 4.0.
- [3] S. T. Stripp, T. Happe, *Dalton Trans.* **2009**, 9960.
- [4] F. Wittkamp, M. Senger, S. T. Stripp, U.-P. Apfel, *Chem. Commun.* **2018**, *54*, 5934–5942.
- [5] C. Baffert, K. Sybirna, P. Ezanno, T. Lautier, V. Hajji, I. Meynial-Salles, P. Soucaille, H. Bottin, C. Léger, *Anal. Chem.* **2012**, *84*, 7999–8005.
- [6] H. Krassen, S. Stripp, G. Von Abendorth, K. Ataka, T. Happe, J. Heberle, *Journal of Biotechnology* **2009**, *142*, 3–9.
- [7] S. Hardt, S. Stapf, D. T. Filmon, J. A. Birrell, O. Rüdiger, V. Fourmond, C. Léger, N. Plumeré, *Nat Catal* **2021**, *4*, 251–258.
- [8] J. Khushvakov, R. Nussbaum, C. Cadoux, J. Duan, S. T. Stripp, R. D. Milton, *Angew Chem Int Ed* **2021**, *60*, 10001–10006.
- [9] S. Ding, A. A. Cargill, I. L. Medintz, J. C. Claussen, *Current Opinion in Biotechnology* **2015**, *34*, 242–250.
- [10] A. Ruff, *Current Opinion in Electrochemistry* **2017**, *5*, 66–73.
- [11] N. Plumeré, O. Rüdiger, A. A. Oughli, R. Williams, J. Vivekananthan, S. Pöller, W. Schuhmann, W. Lubitz, *Nature Chem* **2014**, *6*, 822–827.
- [12] D. Leech, P. Kavanagh, W. Schuhmann, *Electrochimica Acta* **2012**, *84*, 223–234.
- [13] M. Rasmussen, S. Abdellaoui, S. D. Minter, *Biosensors and Bioelectronics* **2016**, *76*, 91–102.
- [14] D. Svedružić, J. L. Blackburn, R. C. Tenent, J.-D. R. Rocha, T. B. Vinzant, M. J. Heben, P. W. King, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2011**, *133*, 4299–4306.
- [15] Y. Liu, J. Zhang, Y. Cheng, S. P. Jiang, *ACS Omega* **2018**, *3*, 667–676.
- [16] M. A. Alonso-Lomillo, O. Rüdiger, A. Maroto-Valiente, M. Velez, I. Rodríguez-Ramos, F. J. Muñoz, V. M. Fernández, A. L. De Lacey, *Nano Lett.* **2007**, *7*, 1603–1608.
- [17] A. R. Pereira, J. C. P. De Souza, R. M. Iost, F. C. P. F. Sales, F. N. Crespiho, *Journal of Electroanalytical Chemistry* **2016**, *780*, 396–406.
- [18] M. Hambourger, M. Gervaldo, D. Svedruzic, P. W. King, D. Gust, M. Ghirardi, A. L. Moore, T. A. Moore, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2008**, *130*, 2015–2022.
- [19] K. Holá, M. V. Pavliuk, B. Németh, P. Huang, L. Zdražil, H. Land, G. Berggren, H. Tian, *ACS Catal.* **2020**, *10*, 9943–9952.
- [20] J. L. Olloqui-Sariego, J. J. Calvente, R. Andreu, *Current Opinion in Electrochemistry* **2021**, *26*, 100658.
- [21] I. Mazurenko, R. Clément, D. Byrne-Kodjabachian, A. De Poulpiquet, S. Tsujimura, E. Lojou, *Journal of Electroanalytical Chemistry* **2018**, *812*, 221–226.
- [22] I. Mazurenko, A. De Poulpiquet, E. Lojou, *Current Opinion in Electrochemistry* **2017**, *5*, 74–84.
- [23] D. H. Nam, J. Z. Zhang, V. Andrei, N. Kornienko, N. Heidary, A. Wagner, K. Nakanishi, K. P. Sokol, B. Slater, I. Zebger, S. Hofmann, J. C. Fontecilla-Camps, C. B. Park, E. Reisner, *Angew Chem Int Ed* **2018**, *57*, 10595–10599.
- [24] D. Mersch, C.-Y. Lee, J. Z. Zhang, K. Brinkert, J. C. Fontecilla-Camps, A. W. Rutherford, E. Reisner, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2015**, *137*, 8541–8549.
- [25] Y. Liu, S. Webb, P. Moreno-García, A. Kulkarni, P. Maroni, P. Broekmann, R. D. Milton, *JACS Au* **2023**, *3*, 124–130.
- [26] E. Edwardes Moore, S. J. Cobb, A. M. Coito, A. R. Oliveira, I. A. C. Pereira, E. Reisner, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* **2022**, *119*, e2114097119.
- [27] P. G. Hoertz, Z. Chen, C. A. Kent, T. J. Meyer, *Inorg. Chem.* **2010**, *49*, 8179–8181.
- [28] J. Esselborn, N. Muraki, K. Klein, V. Engelbrecht, N. Metzler-Nolte, U.-P. Apfel, E. Hofmann, G. Kurisu, T. Happe, *Chem. Sci.* **2016**, *7*, 959–968.
- [29] L. Liu, S. Yellinek, I. Valdinger, A. Donval, D. Mandler, *Electrochimica Acta* **2015**, *176*, 1374–1381.
- [30] A. Minenkov, S. Hollweger, J. Duchoslav, O. Erdene-Ochir, M. Weise, E. Ermilova, A. Hertwig, M. Schiek, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2024**, *16*, 9517–9531.
- [31] P. M. S. Monk, C. M. Man, n.d.
- [32] P. Ciocci, J.-F. Lemineur, J.-M. Noël, C. Combellas, F. Kanoufi, *Electrochimica Acta* **2021**, *386*, 138498.
- [33] M. E. Ahmed, D. Saha, L. Wang, M. Gennari, S. Ghosh Dey, V. Artero, A. Dey, C. Duboc, *ChemElectroChem* **2021**, *8*, 1674–1677.
- [34] A. Goyal, G. Marcandalli, V. A. Mints, M. T. M. Koper, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2020**, *142*, 4154–4161.
- [35] J. Sun, B. V. Velamakanni, W. W. Gerberich, L. F. Francis, *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science* **2004**, *280*, 387–399.
- [36] J. H. Artz, D. W. Mulder, M. W. Ratzloff, C. E. Lubner, O. A. Zadovnyy, A. X. LeVan, S. G. Williams, M. W. W. Adams, A. K. Jones, P. W. King, J. W. Peters, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2017**, *139*, 9544–9550.
- [37] C. Léger, A. K. Jones, S. P. J. Albracht, F. A. Armstrong, *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2002**, *106*, 13058–13063.
- [38] V. Davis, N. Heidary, A. Guet, K. H. Ly, M. Zerball, C. Schulz, N. Michael, R. Von Klitzing, P. Hildebrandt, S. Frielingsdorf, O. Lenz, I. Zebger, A. Fischer, *ACS Catal.* **2023**, *13*, 6312–6327.
- [39] Y. Yang, F. Kong, M. Li, J. Fan, T. Qiu, *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy* **2019**, *213*, 64–72.
- [40] M. Collinson, E. F. Bowden, *Langmuir* **1992**, *8*, 2552–2559.
- [41] J. M. Kuchenreuther, C. S. Grady-Smith, A. S. Bingham, S. J. George, S. P. Cramer, J. R. Swartz, *PLoS ONE* **2010**, *5*, e15491.
- [42] O. Lampret, J. Duan, E. Hofmann, M. Winkler, F. A. Armstrong, T. Happe, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* **2020**, *117*, 20520–20529.
- [43] M. Razavet, S. C. Davies, D. L. Hughes, J. E. Barclay, D. J. Evans, S. A. Fairhurst, X. Liu, C. J. Pickett, *Dalton Trans.* **2003**.

Entry for the Table of Contents

The metalloenzyme [FeFe]-hydrogenase from *Clostridium pasteurianum* ("Cpl") can be utilized for electroenzymatic hydrogen production under ambient conditions and neutral pH. Mesoporous indium tin oxide (ITO) electrodes have a hierarchical morphology with cavities and well-defined nanoparticle agglomerates, enhancing the electroenzymatic performance and stability of Cpl.

Institute and/or researcher Twitter usernames: @Milton_UNIGE